

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Strategies for promoting golf in countries with low popularity of this sport

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Abstract

The relevance of the topic is due to the need to expand the range of mass sports disciplines and integrate new sports into the culture of various regions. In countries where golf has not yet become widespread, it is often associated with elitism and high financial barriers. This limits the development of sports and distorts its perception in society.

The study aims to analyze and evaluate strategies aimed at popularizing golf in such countries, to identify the most effective approaches to overcoming social, economic, and cultural barriers that hinder its development. Contradictions have been identified related to the availability of golf, high infrastructure costs, and limited support from the private sector in emerging economies.

The conclusion is formulated that the successful promotion of golf requires a combination of educational programs, the use of modern technologies, partnerships with business structures, and the creation of accessible infrastructure. However, it is necessary to adapt strategies for each State, taking into account its specifics. That is why, within the framework of the article, special attention is paid to the systematization of their advantages and the most obvious limitations. The materials will be useful for sports managers, organizers of sports events, government agencies, as well as investors interested in the development of sports.

Keywords: Business; golf; Infrastructure; Mass events; Education; Partnership; Promotion; Social inclusion; technology

1. Introduction

Golf, as a sport, is characterized by a centuries-old history and is one of the most significant sporting disciplines in several countries (USA, UK, Japan, etc.). Statistical data reveal that from 2016 to 2023, the number of adult golf players worldwide increased by 10 million people [4]. However, in countries where golf's popularity is low, the sport is often perceived as an elitist pastime [2, 8], which slows its widespread adoption among the general population. To address this issue successfully, specific strategies must be developed that not only overcome existing challenges but also contribute to a systematic increase in interest in golf. This is why contemporary researchers are exploring the key mechanisms and promotion methods, analyzing the social, economic, and cultural factors that influence the perception of this sport, and assessing the prospects for its integration into the sporting culture of countries where its popularity remains low.

2. Material and methods

The methods used in the preparation of this article include comparison, systematization, generalization, and analysis of scientific publications. The literature highlights the following research areas: the impact of golf on socio-economic development, tourism, public perception, and issues of sustainable development.

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For instance, T. Eleftheriou's work explores the global influence of golf and its economic potential. The author describes its impact on infrastructure and the tourism industry, while also analyzing the global rise in golf participation [2], contributing to the evaluation of the effectiveness of strategies to increase its popularity.

Research related to the influence of tourism on golf development is presented in articles by Gerda K. Priestley and Ali A.J. Mohd with co-authors [3, 6]. They analyze the influence of golf tourism on infrastructure planning and economic aspects, which is particularly significant for countries where this sport is only beginning to develop. The experience of golf tourism in Malaysia, Thailand, and Indonesia is compared, with attention given to the specifics of infrastructure development in these countries.

Another area of research focuses on local perceptions of golf, as detailed in the work of H.W. Kim and Il.Mi. Chung [5]. Additionally, Ja.Ju. Nam and M. Kim assess satisfaction with golf participation and the impact of costs, which may help in proposing strategies to reduce barriers [7].

Publications on the development of the golf industry during the pandemic and in specific countries, such as those by P. Park and Ja.K. Shin, examine measures to revive the industry during a crisis and the use of innovative approaches to its development [8, 9]. This serves as a useful experience for countries where golf has not yet achieved high popularity.

Special attention is also paid to issues of sustainability and social responsibility in the golf industry, as discussed in the work of H. Xu and colleagues [10]. They examine the situation in China in terms of ecology and sustainability.

Thus, the scientific literature reveals a diversity of approaches, ranging from the economic and tourism potential of golf to ecological sustainability and public perception. These studies and their valuable insights can help in developing effective promotion strategies.

3. Results and discussion

The strategic foundation for promoting golf in countries where this sport has low popularity is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Strategic foundations for the promotion of golf in countries with low popularity of this sport [1, 5, 6]

One of the fundamental steps for developing golf in these countries is the implementation of educational initiatives aimed at engaging children and youth. Incorporating golf into school physical education programs helps generate interest among younger generations and dispels the myth that golf is an activity solely for the elite. For the successful realization of this strategy, it is necessary to tailor curricula to the specific needs of local schools, ensure the availability of specialized equipment, and train qualified coaches and teachers who can inspire students.

A critical aspect of this development is the creation of infrastructure for school golf programs, including mini-courses and practice areas. Regular intra-school and inter-school tournaments would not only solidify theoretical knowledge in practice but also create an engaging competitive environment that motivates young athletes to continue participating.

One of the limiting factors for the development of golf in countries with low popularity is insufficient infrastructure and the high cost of participation. Golf is often associated with expensive clubs, paid access to courses, and the need for costly equipment. To change this perception, measures are required to democratize access to golf.

An example of an effective solution is the construction of public golf courses that are accessible to all segments of the population. These facilities can be funded by government programs or public-private partnerships. Additionally, it is advisable to develop equipment rental services and offer discounted conditions for beginner athletes to make golf more appealing to individuals from various income levels.

Modern information technologies open up additional avenues and guidelines for promoting the sport in countries where it has yet to gain widespread popularity. The creation of mobile applications, online educational courses, and virtual simulators enables potential players to learn basic skills without having to visit specialized courses, which is especially important for regions with underdeveloped infrastructure.

In addition, digital platforms facilitate the creation of online communities where beginners can fully exchange experiences, participate in virtual competitions, and receive support from more experienced players. The use of social media and platforms for publishing instructional videos, content, and broadcasting tournaments can capture the attention of a younger audience and significantly increase interest in the sport.

Figure 2 Areas of private business participation in golf promotion [3, 7, 9]

Organizing events related to golf is another element of the promotion strategy—large-scale open tournaments, festivals, and exhibition performances by renowned athletes should be considered "catalysts" for growing interest in the sport. It is important that these events not be limited to professional audiences but be aimed at the broader public.

As for the events themselves, it is preferable to accompany them with cultural programs, fairs, and exhibitions to position golf as a family activity, thus creating a positive image of the sport in public perception. Exhibition performances and meetings with famous golfers will give an additional boost to youth interest, providing strong motivation for further involvement.

Private businesses can play a highly productive role in promoting golf (Fig. 2), particularly through sponsorship and marketing programs. Large corporations are encouraged to invest in the development of golf clubs, support youth

programs, and finance major tournaments and media campaigns. Organizations such as sports equipment manufacturers, travel agencies, and the hospitality industry view the development of golf as a marketing opportunity that opens new pathways for interaction between sports and business enterprises.

One of the successful models to recognize is the creation of joint programs with the tourism sector, where golf becomes part of the offering for foreign tourists. For countries with well-developed tourism infrastructure, it makes sense to promote this type of sport as an additional entertainment option for visitors while also generating interest among the local population.

Golf, like other sports, must consider the cultural and social characteristics of each country. Promotion through programs aimed at expanding accessibility for different social groups, including women, people with disabilities, and ethnic minorities, is highly significant. Such programs help integrate golf into the national culture and overcome stereotypes regarding its inaccessibility to the general public.

Creating inclusive conditions for playing golf contributes to the formation of a more tolerant and open sports environment, fostering the sport's growing popularity.

As a result of examining the strategies, Table 1 has been compiled to systematize their advantages and limitations.

Table 1 Advantages and limitations of golf promotion strategies in countries with low popularity (compiled by the author)

Strategy	Advantages	Limitations
Educational programs and school sections	Fosters interest from an early age. Develops skills through systematic training.	Requires significant investment in infrastructure and coach training. Results may not be immediately apparent.
Mass events and tournaments	Attracts a wide audience. Creates a positive image of golf.	One-time effect if events are not held regularly. High organizational costs.
Partnership with business	Additional funding. Opportunity to attract new players through corporate networks and media.	Depends on business interest. Limited resources in countries with low economic development.
Creating accessible infrastructure	Reduces barriers to participation. Expands opportunities for engagement.	High costs for the construction and maintenance of courses. Requires long-term implementation.
Use of digital technologies	Enables online learning. Engages youth through social media and platforms.	Requires stable internet access and technology availability. May not reach older audiences.
Social inclusion and diversity	Expands the audience by making golf accessible to various social groups. Creates a tolerant sports environment.	Requires a specialized approach for each target group. Cultural barriers may be difficult to overcome.

Thus, promotion requires consideration of all nuances, as each strategic direction, despite its advantages, presents certain barriers

4. Conclusion

The development of golf in countries with low popularity requires an approach that takes into account a variety of factors—from the creation of accessible infrastructure and the implementation of educational programs to the use of modern digital technologies and collaboration with entrepreneurial structures. A key aspect of the successful implementation of these strategies is their adaptation to local social and cultural conditions to make golf appealing and accessible to a broad segment of the population.

The main advantages of most strategic directions lie in the potential to expand the audience and improve the image of golf as an accessible sport. However, significant financial investments and the long-term return on many initiatives (such as the creation of infrastructure and the organization of large-scale events) often pose serious challenges to their implementation.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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